

Anna ZHORNIK

*Graduate of the first (bachelor's) level of higher education
Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics
Kharkiv, Ukraine*

Serhii VASYLYK

*Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor,
Associate Professor of the Department of Management and Business
Kharkiv National University of Economics
Kharkiv, Ukraine*

METHODOLOGY OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: THE KEY TO SUCCESSFUL AND EFFECTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF KNOWLEDGE

Анотація. У статті підкреслено важливість планування науково-дослідної роботи. Наголошується на критичній ролі ретельного планування в дослідженні. Підкреслюється, що чітка структура та добре продумана стратегія є основою успішних і продуктивних досліджень.

Ключові слова: методи дослідження, емпіричне дослідження, теоретичне дослідження, кількісне дослідження, якісне дослідження.

Abstract. The article emphasizes the importance of planning research work. Emphasis is placed on the critical role of careful planning in research. It is highlighted that a clear structure and a well-thought-out strategy are the foundation for successful and productive research.

Keywords: research methods, empirical research, theoretical research, quantitative research, qualitative research.

Statement of the problem and its relevance. In the modern world, where knowledge is updated at an incredible speed, and science is becoming more and more dynamic, the methodology of scientific research acquires special importance. It acts not only as a set of methods and techniques, but also as a basis for the formation of a scientific outlook, the ability to think clearly and logically, generate new ideas and find effective ways to implement them.

The relevance of the research topic is determined by the following factors:

The growing role of science in all spheres of society. Scientific research becomes the driving force of progress, and its results are used to solve the most pressing problems of humanity.

Complication of research objects and subjects. This requires the use of more advanced methods and techniques of scientific knowledge.

The need to increase the efficiency of scientific research. In conditions of limited resources, it is important to make maximum use of the possibilities of modern scientific methodology.

Analysis of basic research and publications. Scientific research is a dynamic and multifaceted process aimed at expanding the boundaries of human knowledge. Successful research requires not only a deep understanding of the research topic, but also a clear methodological basis. This topic was researched by: D. M. Stechenko, O. S. Chmyr,

O. V. Krushelnytska's textbooks "Basics of the scientific research", V. I. Krutov, I. M. Hrushka, V. V. Popova and others "Methodology and organization of scientific research", A. S. Filipenko "Basics of scientific research", V. M. Sheiko, N. M. Kushnarenko "Organization and methodology of scientific research activity".

The goal is to study the methodology of scientific research as a key to successful and effective development of knowledge.

Presenting main material. The methodology of scientific research is a system of principles, methods and techniques used to obtain new knowledge. It acts as a framework that organizes and structures research activity, ensuring its systematicity, reasonableness and effectiveness [5].

When characterizing scientific research, the following distinguishing features are usually indicated:

- this is necessarily a purposeful process, the achievement is realized set goal, clearly formulated tasks;
- it is a process aimed at finding new things, at creativity, at discovering the unknown, at putting forward original ideas, at new illumination of the discussed issues;
- it is characterized by systematicity: here both the research process itself and its results are organized and brought into the system;
- it is characterized by strict evidence, consistent substantiation of the generalizations and conclusions made [2].

The choice of research methodology depends on the purpose and tasks of the research, the object and phenomenon being studied, as well as on the available resources. The researcher should thoroughly study the existing methodologies and choose the one that best suits his needs.

Successful and effective research is the result not only of the knowledge and experience of the researcher, but also of the correct methodology. Adherence to methodological principles allows the researcher to gain new knowledge about the world, make scientific discoveries and develop new theories, which contributes to the development of science and society.

Method (Greek – way of knowing) – in the broadest sense words are "a way to something", a way of the subject's activity in any of its forms.

The term "methodology" has two main meanings: a system of defined methods and techniques used in one or another field of activity (in science, politics, art, etc.); the doctrine of this system, the general theory of the method, the theory in action.

Formulation of the purpose and tasks of the research: a clear definition of the purpose of the research and specification of the tasks necessary for its achievement determine the vector of research activity.

Literature review: a thorough study of already existing research on a given topic allows the researcher to avoid duplication, outline new aspects and form his own research concept [1].

The choice of research methods: the selection of methods adequate to the tasks and research questions is the key to obtaining reliable and relevant results. relying on the system of methodological principles, the researcher determines:

- object and subject of research;
- the sequence of their solution;
- applied methods.

Two main stages, two characteristic levels can be conventionally distinguished scientific research:

- a) empirical;
- b) theoretical.

The empirical stage is related to the acquisition and primary processing original factual material. They usually share: the facts of reality and scientific facts.

Facts of reality are events, phenomena that happened or are happening in reality, they are different sides, properties, relationships of the subjects objects.

Scientific facts are facts of reality reflected by consciousness, and necessarily verified, understood and recorded in the language of science in the form of empirical judgments [3].

Expected results of scientific research are preliminary descriptions of theories, concepts, regularities, functional and analytical dependencies, methods, models, schemes, methods, algorithms, other provisions that will be created, changed and/or supplemented by the author during the performance of scientific research.

In the Law of Ukraine on scientific and scientific and technical activity (Vidomosti of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2016, No. 3, Art. 25) terms and their definitions are given with changes, in particular:

“...22) scientific result – new scientific knowledge obtained in the process of fundamental or applied scientific research and recorded on information carriers. The scientific result can be in the form of a report, a published scientific article, a scientific report, a scientific report on scientific research work, a monographic study, a scientific discovery, a draft of a regulatory act, a regulatory document or scientific and methodological documents, the preparation of which requires conducting relevant scientific research or contains a scientific component, then what; [6].

...27) scientific and technical (applied) result – new or significantly improved materials, products, processes, devices, technologies, systems, new or significantly improved services, implemented during applied scientific research, scientific and technical (experimental) development new constructive or technological solutions, completed tests, developments implemented or may be implemented in public practice. A scientific and technical (applied) result can be in the form of a draft project, an experimental (research) sample or its working model, design or technological documentation for scientific and technical products, a test sample, a draft regulatory act, a regulatory document or scientific methodical documents, etc.”.

The scientific novelty of the idea (theme), the obtained results is a feature that characterizes the obtained results and research in general by the concept of "first time" [7]. This concept means in science the lack (or limitation) of similar results before their publication. For many branches of science, novelty is found in the presence of newly formulated and substantively substantiated theoretical propositions, developed principles, models, methods, and established dependencies. Those provisions of research that contribute to the further development of science or its individual directions may be new [7].

According to the place of the obtained knowledge, three are distinguished among the known scientific data

novelty levels [7]:

– transformation of known data, their fundamental change (characterized by knowledge that is fundamentally new in this field, which does not simply supplement known provisions, but is something independent);

– expansion, addition of known data (a new result expands known theoretical or practical provisions, adds new elements to them, supplements knowledge in this field without changing their essence);

– clarification, concretization of known data, extension of known results to a new class of objects, systems (a new result clarifies what is known, specifies certain provisions relating to individual cases, and known methods or methods can be developed and extended to a new class of objects, systems, phenomena).

Thus, novelty in scientific research performs functions [4]:

– ascertaining at the level of discovery or invention (new conceptual statements, theories and approaches that radically change scientific knowledge are obtained);

– developing at the level of expansion and deepening;

– specifying at the level of detail;

– complementary at the level of clarification.

Theoretical significance is a characteristic of the importance, provability and conceptuality of the obtained results and their scientific perspective [4].

Conclusion. The scientific novelty of the expected / obtained results must be proven on the basis of their meaningful comparison with existing analogues in world science, and the advantages of the results to be obtained over the existing ones must be proven.

Analysis and interpretation of results: critical analysis of the obtained data, their generalization and interpretation allow drawing conclusions and formulating new knowledge.

Prospective further explorations. Presentation of research results: clear and concise presentation of research results in the form of an article, dissertation, monograph or report makes them accessible to the scientific community and contributes to the implementation of the acquired knowledge in practice.

Saving time and resources: a clear methodology allows the researcher to use time and resources rationally, avoiding

Increasing research efficiency: the researcher's methodological armament makes it possible to focus on the most important aspects of the research.

Increasing the probability of success: A clear methodology significantly increases the probability of obtaining reliable.

Universality: the methodological principles of research have a universal character and can be applied in any scientific field.

References

1. Методологія наукових досліджень: навч.-метод. посіб. / В. С. Антонюк, Л. Г. Полонський, В. І. Аверченков, Ю. А. Малахов. Київ : НТУУ "КПІ", 2015. 276 с. <https://ela.kpi.ua/handle/123456789/18679>
2. Мокін Б. І., Мокін О. Б. Методологія та організація наукових досліджень : навч. посіб. Вінниця : ВНТУ, 2014. 180 с. https://ir.lib.vntu.edu.ua/bitstream/handle/123456789/11644/Mokin_metodologia_2014.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
3. Чмиленко Ф. О., Жук Л. П. Посібник до вивчення дисципліни "Методологія та організація наукових досліджень". Дніпропетровськ : РВВ ДНУ, 2014. 48 с. <http://kist.ntu.edu.ua/textPhD/mond.pdf>
4. Юринець В. Є. Методологія наукових досліджень: навчальний посібник. Львів : ЛНУ імені Івана Франка, 2011. 178 с. https://institut-zerna.com/education/docs/silabus_navdoslidnyka/metodoligiya-naukovyh-doslidgen.pdf

5. Основи методології та організації наукових досліджень : навч. посіб. для студентів, курсантів, аспірантів і ад'юнктів / за ред. А. Є. Конверського. Київ : Центр учбової літератури, 2010. 352 с.
https://biology.univ.kiev.ua/images/stories/Upload/Kafedry/Biofizyky/2014/konversky_osn_metod_ta_org_nayk_dosl.pdf
6. Технологія наукових досліджень і технічної творчості / Е. В. Гаврилов, М. Ф. Дмитриченко, В. К. Доля, О. Т. Лановий, І. Е. Линник; за заг. ред. М. Ф. Дмитриченка. Київ : Знання України, 2007. 318 с.
7. Основи наукових досліджень. Організація наукових досліджень : конспект лекцій для студентів магістратури приладобудівного факультету / Упоряд. Н. І. Бурау. Київ : НТУУ "КПІ", 2007. 33 с.